

Long-read sequencing for epigenomic studies in the fields of Ecology and Evolution

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Abstract

Epigenetic mechanisms, including DNA methylation, play crucial roles in regulating gene expression, influencing phenotypic variation, and facilitating responses to environmental pressures. Bisulfite sequencing has long been the gold standard for studying DNA methylation in ecological and evolutionary contexts. However, this method has significant limitations, such as an inability to distinguish C/T SNPs from methylation calls, poor resolution of structural variants and an inability to detect specific modifications like 5-hydroxy-methylcytosine. The advent of long-read sequencing offers a powerful alternative by directly sequencing native DNA to overcome these limitations. Long-read sequencing enables the accurate detection of DNA methylation and other epigenetic marks, facilitates haplotype phasing for allele-specific studies, and resolves complex structural variation. Although challenges such as computational demands and elevated costs remain, rapid advancements in sequencing technologies, algorithmic efficiency, and declining costs are improving its accessibility. This perspective highlights the transformative potential of long-read sequencing on the study of epigenetics and genome evolution, offering a powerful tool to address critical questions in ecology and evolution.

35 DNA methylation in the fields of Ecology and Evolution

36

37 Epigenetic mechanisms, including DNA methylation, histone modifications, and small RNAs,
38 are molecular markers that regulate gene expression. Epigenetic marks can be transmitted
39 through mitotic divisions and, in some cases, across meiotic divisions (Richards, 2006;
40 Heard & Martienssen 2014). DNA methylation, in particular, has received the most focus in
41 ecology and evolution due to its increased stability relative to histone modifications and small
42 non-coding RNAs (Verhoeven et al., 2016). Among different types of DNA methylation, 5-
43 methylcytosine (5mC) is the most widely studied, as it is the primary methylation form in
44 eukaryotes (Goll & Bestor, 2005; Breiling & Lyko, 2015). Like other epigenetic mechanisms,
45 DNA methylation is especially critical in tissue differentiation during development (Smith and
46 Meissner, 2013; Smith et al. 2024).

47

48 By regulating gene expression, DNA methylation can contribute to phenotypic variation and
49 may influence an organism's fitness in its environment. DNA methylation patterns are
50 dependent on genetically-encoded enzymatic machinery and are, therefore, influenced by
51 genetic background (Adrian-Kalchhauser et al., 2020; Richards, 2006; Sepers et al., 2023;
52 Taudt et al., 2016). However, epigenetic patterns are dynamic and may change due to
53 maintenance errors and environmental shifts. Such ability to respond to environmental
54 variation makes DNA methylation a plausible mechanism of phenotypic plasticity (Duncan et
55 al., 2014; Hu & Barrett, 2017; Husby, 2022). As such, numerous studies have demonstrated
56 associations between DNA methylation and environmental differences, including gradients of
57 ocean acidification (Lee et al., 2022), different climatic conditions (Wogan et al., 2020),
58 salinity (Lira-Medeiros et al., 2010; Heckwolf et al., 2020), sulfidic environments (Kelley et
59 al., 2021), temperature (Hu and Barrett, 2017; McCaw et al., 2020), heat-stress (López et al.
60 2024), and parasite exposure (Sagonas et al. 2020), among others.

61

62 Most critically, DNA methylation can be passed on across generations in many taxa
63 (Anastasiadi et al., 2021; Fitz-James & Cavalli, 2022), including flowering plants (Schmid et
64 al., 2018; van der Graaf et al., 2015; López et al. 2024), fish (Heckwolf et al., 2020; Kelley et
65 al., 2021), mammals (Skvortsova et al., 2018), and insects (Li-Byarlay et al., 2013; Li-
66 Byarlay 2016; Wang et al., 2016; Wang and Li-Byarlay, 2015; Yagound et al., 2020; Yan et
67 al., 2015). Because DNA methylation can respond to environmental pressures and be
68 transmitted to subsequent generations, it has drawn interest as a possible mechanism for
69 transgenerational plasticity (Jablonka and Lamb, 1998; Jablonka and Raz, 2009, Laland et
70 al. 2014).

71

72 Beyond these functions, DNA methylation also contributes to genome regulation and genetic
73 differentiation, and thus genome evolution. It plays a key role in suppressing repetitive
74 elements in heterochromatin, and stabilizing these areas to maintain genomic integrity,
75 particularly in plants (Badauel and Colot, 2021; Cortijo et al., 2014; Law and Jacobsen, 2010;
76 Schübeler, 2015). In addition, 5mC is more prone to transition into thymine (*i.e.*, C-to-T
77 mutations) than any other point mutation (Holliday & Grigg, 1993; Ossowski et al., 2010;
78 Tomkova & Schuster-Böckler, 2018), introducing a mutational bias that could create genetic
79 variation and lead to genetic differentiation. As such, DNA methylation can influence

80 evolution over different timescales, from immediate acclimation effects to genetic evolution
81 (de Carvalho & Planidin, 2024; Laine et al., 2022; Venney et al., 2023). Recent empirical
82 studies illustrate how DNA methylation may contribute to population divergence, adaptation,
83 reproductive isolation, and speciation (Dubin et al., 2015; Schmid et al., 2018; Heckwolf et
84 al., 2020; Vernaz et al., 2021, 2022; Hu and Barrett, 2023; Laporte et al., 2019).

85
86 Nevertheless, important questions remain. For example, the extent to which DNA
87 methylation affects phenotype and contributes to short-term acclimation in response to
88 environmental change remains unclear, though mounting evidence shows that epigenetic
89 variation is linked to phenotypic variation (Anastasiadi et al. 2021). Most studies have yet to
90 determine to what extent DNA methylation operates independently of genetic background, or
91 to what extent variation in DNA methylation generates adaptive genetic variation via point
92 mutations and changes in genome structure. Understanding this distinction is critical for
93 assessing whether DNA methylation serves as a direct driver of key ecological and
94 evolutionary processes (e.g., adaptation, transgenerational plasticity, and persistence in
95 changing environments) or merely reflects genetic variation and stochasticity (see Husby,
96 2022; McGuigan et al., 2021; Richards et al., 2017; for reviews). These knowledge gaps
97 underscore the need for reliable methodologies to study DNA methylation to better
98 understand its ecological and evolutionary implications on different timescales. This
99 perspective focuses on these approaches, examining current methods and highlighting
100 promising novel technologies to advance the field.

101
102 ***Bisulfite sequencing: the current status quo for DNA methylation studies:*** Currently,
103 bisulfite sequencing is the gold standard for analyzing DNA methylation in ecology and
104 evolution studies, being the primary technology used in most of the empirical studies cited
105 above. It offers genome-wide detection of 5mC with single base pair resolution. In this
106 method, genomic DNA is treated with sodium bisulfite, which deaminates unmethylated
107 cytosines to uracil, while methylated cytosines remain intact (Frommer et al. 1992). The
108 treated DNA can then be sequenced using high-throughput short-read sequencing, allowing
109 the estimation of DNA methylation levels at each cytosine. Whole-genome bisulfite
110 sequencing (WGBS) can theoretically cover all cytosine sites (Cokus et al. 2008), although
111 some coverage biases may persist (Olova et al. 2018). Alternatively, reduced representation
112 bisulfite sequencing (RRBS) uses the restriction enzyme *MspI*, which targets CCGG motifs
113 to enrich for methylated regions. This reduces costs and the amount of sequencing required,
114 but restricts the analysis to *MspI* sites only (Gu et al., 2011). Other reduced representation
115 methods are commonly used, including methylated DNA immunoprecipitation sequencing
116 (MeDIPseq). However, WGBS is becoming more common as the costs of high-throughput
117 sequencing continue to decline, even for non-model organisms.

118
119 While highly effective and widely used, bisulfite sequencing has several limitations (**Fig. 1**).
120 For example, bisulfite sequencing cannot distinguish between 5-methylcytosine (5mC) and
121 5-hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC), as both are unaffected by bisulfite conversion. Bisulfite
122 treatment also degrades DNA, which has prompted the development and use of enzymatic
123 methylation sequencing methods (EM-seq) that reduce DNA degradation (Vaisvila et al.
124 2021) and detect 5hmC (Erlitzki and Kohli 2024). Additionally, bisulfite sequencing cannot

125 distinguish between T reads that result from C/T SNPs and unmethylated cytosines, which
126 creates artefacts during methylation calling (**Fig. 1C**). This issue is particularly critical in
127 population and comparative epigenetic studies and experiments with small sample sizes,
128 where C/T SNPs are likely to be more prevalent among the samples. Newly developed
129 protocols work to mitigate this issue, such as the development of SNP detection methods
130 from bisulfite sequencing data (e.g., Gao et al. 2015; Liu et al. 2012). However, these
131 methods rely on strand-specific SNP detection (i.e. a SNP must be detected on both strands
132 to be distinguished from bisulfite conversion), making them less sensitive than conventional
133 SNP calling from short-read data. An alternative approach involves generating genomic
134 sequences for each bisulfite-treated sample to distinguish SNPs from unmethylated
135 cytosines, though this increases overall costs.

136

137 Other challenges remain, such as multi-mapping issues during alignment due to structural
138 variants (SVs) or copy number variants (CNVs) present in the reference (**Fig. 1B**).
139 Furthermore, sample-specific CNVs (i.e. present in the sample but not the reference) may
140 result in the detection of erroneous, chimeric methylation patterns – a phenomenon termed
141 pseudo-heterozygosity (see Jaegle et al. 2023). Thus, effectively mitigating these artefacts in
142 short-read-based analyses requires significant additional sequencing and/or computational
143 effort. Bisulfite sequencing remains a valuable epigenomics tool and has led to many
144 important findings in ecological, evolutionary, biomedical and agricultural research, though
145 careful consideration and additional time, computational, and/or financial investments are
146 required to minimize artefacts.

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Figure 1: Processes, possibilities, and limitations of DNA methylation analysis using short-read (left) and long-read (right) whole genome sequencing. (A) Short-read sequencing relies on bisulfite conversion, or enzymatic methyl-seq (EM-seq), to detect

151 methylated cytosines. Bisulfite conversion is currently the most widely used but damages
152 DNA. Long-read sequencing relies on native DNA sequencing and does not require
153 additional treatments, though it requires high-quality, high-molecular weight DNA. **(B)**
154 Different colours of lines represent different genomic motifs. When the sequence data is
155 aligned to a reference genome, long-read sequencing is more effective at identifying
156 structural variants (SVs) and copy number variants (CNVs) since the longer reads are more
157 likely to discriminate between duplicated regions of the genome. Long-read sequencing also
158 facilitates easier genome phasing, which allows the detection of allele-specific DNA
159 methylation. **(C)** Bisulfite conversion affects both 5-methylcytosine (5mC) and 5-
160 hydroxymethylcytosine (5hmC), preventing discrimination between the two modifications. An
161 alternative form of EM-seq can detect 5hmC specifically, but requires additional sequencing.
162 Moreover, since bisulfite sequencing analysis is based on the number of C (methylated) and
163 T (unmethylated) reads, C/T SNPs (and G/A SNPs to account for the G position of CpG
164 sites) can introduce artefacts into DNA methylation calling. The higher the frequency of T
165 alleles, the lower the estimate of percent DNA methylation at this site. Long-read sequencing
166 directly detects DNA modifications based on altered sequencing kinetics or ionic signals.
167 PacBio sequencing can specifically detect 5mC in a CpG context, and Nanopore sequencing
168 can detect 5mC in CpG, CHH, and CHG contexts; 5hmC; 4mC; and 6mA. **(D)** After DNA
169 methylation estimates are produced, the same DNA methylation analysis programs can be
170 used for both short-read and long-read sequencing. **(E)** A summary of the pros and cons of
171 each method.

172

173 **Long-read sequencing to mitigate bisulfite sequencing artefacts:** Long-read sequencing
174 offers the potential to mitigate many of the limitations of bisulfite sequencing, while providing
175 richer epigenetic information (**Fig. 1**). Currently, long-read epigenetic sequencing is
176 conducted using (1) Oxford Nanopore technology (Deamer et al. 2016), which detects shifts
177 in electric signal as single bases pass through a nanopore, and (2) PacBio single-molecule
178 real-time sequencing (Flusberg et al. 2010), which analyses polymerase kinetics in a
179 sequencing-by-synthesis approach. By sequencing native DNA molecules directly, long-read
180 sequencing technologies avoid the need for heavy fragmentation, treatment, or amplification,
181 enabling the sequencing of multiple kilobases of DNA at a time. These longer reads
182 circumvent many of the limitations seen in bisulfite sequencing, particularly by enabling the
183 identification of SVs and CNVs and reducing pseudo-heterozygosity (Lavrichenko et al.
184 2021; O'Neill et al. 2024, Liu & Conesa 2025).

185

186 Unlike bisulfite sequencing, neither Nanopore nor PacBio methylation calling is affected by
187 SNPs at CpG sites. They first detect the nucleotide, then slight differences in signal are
188 interpreted as the presence or absence of a base modification based on their respective
189 algorithms. While bisulfite sequencing can only identify 5mC and cannot distinguish it from
190 5hmC, PacBio sequencing can accurately identify 5mC in a CpG context (though CHH and
191 CHG contexts are not currently supported; Rhoads & Au 2015). On the other hand,
192 Nanopore sequencing can distinguish between 5mC, 5hmC, 4-methylcytosine (4mC), and 6-
193 methyladenine (6mA) in all contexts (Tourancheau et al. 2021; Rand et al. 2017), though
194 there is some question about the accuracy of detecting low frequency modifications (Kong et
195 al., 2024).

196

197 Therefore, long-read sequencing has the potential to significantly advance epigenetic
198 research. Some of these tools have already been applied to epigenetic studies, particularly
199 in fields such as biomedical science, agricultural research, and metagenomics (**Box 1**).
200 However, the use of long-read sequencing for DNA methylation detection in ecological and
201 evolutionary studies is still in its early stages, with current studies being predominantly
202 descriptive, focusing on profiling of DNA methylation variation across the genome in non-
203 model organisms (Flack et al., 2023; McEvoy et al., 2024; Schall et al., 2023). These
204 advancements open up promising new avenues for application in ecological and
205 evolutionary studies, which we explore in the following sections.

206

207

208

209 **Box 1: Applications of long-read sequencing for DNA methylation across diverse**
210 **fields.**

211

212 **Prokaryote studies:** The detection of DNA methylation in long-read sequencing has greatly
213 contributed to prokaryotic epigenetics, particularly in metagenomics (i.e., the study of genetic
214 material collected directly from environmental or clinical samples). This technology is widely
215 used for taxonomic differentiation and estimating phylogenetic relationships, as it detects
216 subtle genomic differences between closely related bacterial strains. The detection of
217 genome-wide DNA methylation with increased read length is important for retrieving unique
218 regions computationally, improving the identification of bacterial strains in microbial studies
219 (Seong et al. 2021; Agostinho et al., 2024; Nielsen et al., 2023). While 5mC is the dominant
220 modification in eukaryotes, prokaryotes commonly feature 6mA and 4mC, which can be
221 detected by long-read sequencing technologies. Beyond metagenomics, long-read
222 sequencing enables refined profiling of DNA methylation in prokaryotes allowing better
223 characterization of the relationship with their hosts. For example, Bruneaux et al. (2022)
224 have used experimental evolution assays to establish a link between m6A methylation in the
225 *Serratia marcescens* bacteria with phenotypic traits and their response to temperature shifts.
226 Strikingly, Gopalan-Nair et al. (2024) have shown rapid DNA methylation-based adaptation
227 of the plant pathogen *Ralstonia pseudosolanacearum* to its host plant, showing a direct link
228 between bacterial epigenetic variation and adaptation to a new environment.

229

230 **Biomedical research:** Long-read sequencing has become a cornerstone in biomedical
231 research, particularly in cancer studies. Its ability to provide both high-resolution genetic data
232 and phased DNA methylation information allows for detailed detection of aberrant
233 expression patterns, including those stemming from allelic expression imbalances or gene
234 fusions (Rausch et al., 2023; O'Neill et al., 2024). This dual profiling of genetic and
235 epigenetic modifications has proven valuable for biomedical applications, such as identifying
236 DNA methylation changes and repeat expansions linked to neurodegenerative diseases,
237 observed across both parents and offspring (Fukuda et al., 2021). Furthermore, combining
238 long-read sequencing with machine learning could help in early cancer diagnoses and even
239 allow for sparse methylation profiling during consultation (Simon et al., 2024; Vermeulen et
240 al., 2023). Despite its advantages, challenges remain. Certain genes in cancer genomes

241 exhibit highly complex patterns, including megabase-scale rearrangements, which are
242 difficult to fully resolve even with current long-read sequencing technology (Sakamoto et al.
243 2021).

244

245 **Agricultural and animal science:** DNA methylation is involved in important processes such
246 as crop breeding (Tonosaki et al. 2022), fruit ripening (Song et al. 2024), and stress
247 response in plants (López et al. 2022), as well as animal fertility (Thompson et al. 2020),
248 making it a key target for epigenetic engineering. As such, long-read sequencing has been
249 used to elucidate DNA methylation patterns linked to important traits in crops and animals.
250 For example, deep learning tools like DeepSignal-plant
251 (<https://github.com/PengNi/deepsignal-plant>) can identify more methylated cytosines than
252 bisulfite sequencing, aiding the study of repetitive and polyploid plant genomes (Ni et al.
253 2021). Long-reads have also been used to characterize the epigenome of two maple
254 species, revealing unique methylation patterns in transposable elements (McEvoy et al.
255 2024). Moreover, combining long-read DNA methylation data with Hi-C genomic can offer
256 insights into haplotype differences, which can inform breeding strategies (Gladman et al.
257 2023). Long-read sequencing also allows the detection of higher levels of mobile elements in
258 canine species (Schall et al. 2023) and methylated positions in distal intergenic regions of
259 bulls (López-Catalina et al. 2024), contributing to epigenetic signatures for breeding and
260 animal health.

261

262

263 **Long-read sequencing: the way forward for epigenomic studies**

264

265 Beyond addressing the limitations of bisulfite sequencing, long-read sequencing unlocks
266 novel research opportunities in ecology and evolution that were previously inaccessible or
267 highly challenging with the technologies available. In addition to reducing DNA degradation
268 and resolving the issue of SNPs confounding methylation calls, long read-sequencing offers
269 unique capabilities that pave the way for groundbreaking insights in epigenetic studies.
270 Below, we discuss some of the most promising research avenues enabled by this
271 technology.

272

273 **Structural variation:** Traditionally, studies of the genomic basis of adaptive evolution have
274 focused on SNPs, as they can be effectively profiled with short-read sequencing. However,
275 while less abundant than SNPs, structural variants (SVs) are increasingly recognized for
276 their important role in adaptive evolution (Watson et al., 2022; Thorstensen et al., 2022;
277 Mérot et al., 2023; Hager et al., 2022). SVs include chromosomal inversions, deletions,
278 insertions, duplications, and copy number variants (CNVs), all of which can be extensively
279 profiled using long-read sequencing. For example, Weissensteiner et al (2020) have
280 combined short-read with long-read sequencing in corvids to identify a large long terminal
281 repeat (LTR) retrotransposon acting as a cis-regulatory element, which affects pigment
282 expression and ultimately causes the distinction between hooded and carrion crows.
283 Similarly, Lundberg et al. (2023) have used long-read sequencing to identify a large
284 chromosomal inversion driving divergence in migratory phenotypes of the willow warbler
285 (*Phylloscopus trochilus*; Lundberg et al 2023).

286

287 SVs are often associated with DNA methylation variation (Zhang et al., 2019; Shi et al.,
288 2020). This is because DNA methylation plays a principal role in diverse taxa in silencing of
289 transposable elements (TEs), whose activity can drive SVs across the genome. This
290 relationship is bidirectional (discussed extensively by Baduel & Colot, 2021). On one hand,
291 variation in TE silencing by DNA methylation is associated with the degree of TE
292 mobilization across the genome, generating SV. On the other hand, the emergence of TEs
293 and the resulting SVs can create new targets of DNA methylation, which can lead to DNA
294 methylation variation with potential phenotypic consequences. A notable example is a TE
295 upstream of the *Agouti* gene in mice, which causes ectopic gene expression that leads to
296 altered coat colour and metabolic syndrome unless the TE is methylated (Blewitt et al 2006).
297 Similarly, a TE insertion in African oil palm trees (*Elaeis guineensis*) acts as a premature
298 stop codon which distorts fruit development unless it is methylated (Ong-Abdullah et al
299 2015). In some plant genomes, TE methylation spreads to nearby genes, although its
300 functional consequences remain unclear (Choi & Purugganan, 2018). Furthermore, analysis
301 of 1,107 Arabidopsis methylomes sampled globally revealed that SVs are major drivers of
302 natural variation in DNA methylation (Kawakatsu et al., 2016).

303

304 While many of the aforementioned studies used short-read sequencing, long-read
305 sequencing technologies can identify TEs and SVs in unprecedented detail, accurately
306 identifying small deletions, insertions and inversions of all sizes compared short-read data
307 (Mérot et al. 2023). Therefore, this technology can enable not only the mitigation of biases
308 arising from TEs and other SVs, but also facilitates a deeper integration of SV in studies of
309 epigenome evolution. As such, long-read sequencing can be a powerful tool to advance our
310 understanding of the relationship between DNA methylation and SVs, providing high-
311 resolution insights into both DNA methylation patterns and the structural dynamics of the
312 genome. Most critically, in light of the discovery of varying SV within species allowed by
313 long-read sequencing, we are currently at the beginning of a shift from a single reference
314 genome to a 'pangenome' perspective.

315

316 In a practical sense, a pangenome comprises the assembly and annotation of multiple
317 genomes with the aim of representing the genomic variation of a species (or multiple closely-
318 related species) as opposed to a single reference sequence. The variable gene repertoires
319 revealed by pangenomes beg the question of how epigenetic regulation acts differently for
320 core and dispensable genes, although this question has not been addressed. Moving
321 beyond gene repertoires, pangenome graphs attempt to encapsulate the core sequence and
322 all sequence variants in a graph with edges and nodes (Hickey et al 2023), serving as a
323 catalogue of common SVs present in a species. Recent tools enable short-reads to be
324 aligned to the graph to detect common SVs from short-reads, call SNPs within SVs and even
325 quantify gene expression (Hickey et al 2023, Sibbesen et al 2023). However, to our
326 knowledge, there is currently no mapping software available to align bisulfite short-reads to
327 pangenomes. Beyond the advantages of pangenomes to SV, pangenomes also capture
328 CpG variation between individuals, allowing the identification of a greater number of
329 differentially methylated sites in studies with samples containing genetic variation (Dong et

330 al. 2024). Indeed, the inclusion of epigenetic diversity within the pangenome framework,
331 would further improve their utility.

332

333 With long-read sequencing, it is now feasible to simultaneously profile SVs and epigenetic
334 variation across populations. This integrated approach allows us to examine the role of SV
335 potentially driving epigenomic variation and explore how epigenomic variation is specific to
336 certain SVs (e.g. accessory genes). Ultimately, such integrated approaches are necessary
337 for understanding the molecular basis of phenotypic variation and adaptive evolution.

338

339 **Haplotype phasing for allele-specific studies:** Haplotype phasing is a method used to
340 determine the specific combinations of alleles (haplotypes) inherited from each parent. Long-
341 reads, by nature, will capture variants that are within physical proximity. This allows the
342 creation of phase blocks, where all variants within a single read can be assumed to be from
343 the same homolog and thus “in phase”. Initially developed in human genomics, this process
344 can allow ecological and evolutionary studies to move beyond an individual’s genotype to
345 potentially identify the parent-of-origin of entire chromosome homologs.

346

347 Whilst the above idea is clearly beneficial for the field of population genomics (identifying
348 runs of variants inherited together), it also opens new avenues within epigenomics. Being
349 able to determine long stretches of phased information or indeed whole homologs, enables
350 studies into allele-specific and parent-of-origin epigenetic marks (Bresnahan et al., 2023),
351 which are difficult to identify using short-read data (**Fig. 1B**). Traditionally, to study allele-
352 specific methylation of a site, each short-read this position is located on must also contain a
353 nearby SNP which distinguishes the alleles within the individual. This means that previous
354 work has only been able to examine a relatively small number of positions within a genome
355 (Wu et al. 2020) or has relied on computational prediction tools (e.g., Abante et al. 2020).
356 The application of large haplotype blocks generated by long-read sequencing solves this
357 issue.

358

359 Beyond the benefits of identifying long stretches of haplotype information, it is now also
360 possible to identify the parent-of-origin of entire homologs (i.e. a maternal/paternal
361 chromosome-scale haplotype block). Homologs can be identified using a combination of
362 long-read sequencing and Strand-Seq (Porubsky et al. 2017). Utilizing known parent-of-
363 origin DNA methylation marks from imprinted genes, Akbari et al. (2023) have built on
364 homolog-identification to assign parent-of-origin status to homologs without the need for
365 parental genome sequencing. Utilizing just under 200 imprinted genes, all 22 autosomes of
366 the human genome can be assigned to a parent-of-origin. The identification of imprinted
367 genes in species beyond mammals and plants is extremely limited; adopting these novel
368 protocols from the human genetics field will completely open up this area of research.

369

370 Specific advances which can be made within the fields of ecology and evolution due to long-
371 read haplotype phasing include the identification of allele-specific epigenetic marks driven by
372 *cis*- or *trans*- acting SNPs (influencing the field of population epigenomics). It will also
373 considerably simplify the identification of imprinting systems outside of mammals and plants,
374 providing an ability to test imprinted gene evolutionary theories (e.g. Oldroyd and Yagound

2021). Long-reads will also aid in the identification of environmentally induced epigenetic marks which may be inherited in a parent-of-origin manner, informing sex-specific inheritance in fields such as ecotoxicology (e.g., Faulk et al. 2013). Therefore, long-read sequencing approaches will provide new insights into transgenerational plasticity, a topic of great interest and significance in evolutionary biology.

380

Modifications beyond 5-methylcytosine: Whilst 5mC is the primary focus of studies on DNA methylation, long-read sequencing can detect a variety of epigenetic marks other than 5mC. One of the most studied of these marks is N6-methyladenine (6mA), which plays a functional role in model organisms like *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* that lack 5mC (Greer et al. 2015; Zhang et al. 2015), as well as non-model organisms like *Apis mellifera* (Bresnahan et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021). 6mA has been shown to influence the response to environmental stress and be transmitted between generations (Zhang et al. 2018; Ma et al. 2019), highlighting its potential in ecological and evolutionary research.

390

Unlike short-read sequencing, Nanopore long-read sequencing of native DNA can detect 6mA and other base modifications without chemical conversion, allowing simultaneous profiling of 5mC and 6mA (Zhang et al., 2022a). Additionally, it can differentiate oxidized 5mC marks, such as 5hmC, 5caC, and 5fC. These marks are intermediates in the conversion of 5mC back to cytosine, which are detected as 5mC (5hmC) or cytosine (5caC and 5fC) during bisulfite sequencing (Flusberg et al. 2010; Wescoe et al. 2014; Searle et al. 2023). These marks play a key role in the regulation of 5mC, changing through development and due to phenotypic plasticity (Wossidlo et al. 2011; Sun et al. 2014). Thus, their study can provide deeper mechanistic insight beyond just profiling 5mC. Nanopore sequencing specifically can also identify epigenetic marks on RNA (Parker et al. 2020; Abebe et al. 2022; Wang et al. 2022). Among these, N6-methyladenosine (m6A), distinct from 6mA, is a key regulator of mRNA stability and regulates responses to heat and drought stress in plants (Roundtree et al. 2017; Hou et al. 2022; Sun et al. 2024).

404

Enzymatic conversion can also be used with long-read sequencing to detect other epigenetic marks, such as histone modifications (Yue et al. 2022), chromatin accessibility (Wang et al. 2019; Lee et al. 2020; Shipony et al. 2020) and 3-D chromosome interactions (Liu & Conesa 2025). This will allow the direct study of interactions among 5mC and other epigenetic marks. Furthermore, enzymatic conversion can increase the detection probability of harder to detect marks like 5hmC (Liu et al. 2020). However, use of enzymatic conversion in both these contexts means the loss of some of the benefits of long-read sequencing over next-generation techniques (**Fig. 1**).

413

While studies of non-5mC epigenetic marks using long-read sequencing are largely restricted to model species, there are some studies of 6mA in non-model plants (Chachar et al. 2021; Zhang et al. 2022b, 2023). The use of long-read sequencing can thus help improve the detection of these understudied base modifications in non-model species, clarifying their relevance for ecological and evolutionary processes. As they are less studied, algorithms for the detection of low frequency base modifications such as m6A (Liu et al. 2019), oxidised

420 5mC (Wescoe et al. 2014; Searle et al. 2023), and 6mA (Zhong et al. 2023) have lower
421 fidelity than calling 5mC sites, but methods are improving (Kulkarni et al., 2024).

422

423 **Comparative epigenomics:** DNA methylation is fairly conserved across the tree of life
424 (Feng et al., 2010a; Zemach et al., 2010; Klughammer et al., 2023). However, its functions
425 and patterns can vary widely. For example, many genomes are globally methylated except
426 at promoter regions, which are typically unmethylated (Jones, 2012), though genome-wide
427 methylation levels follow taxonomic divides (Klughammer et al. 2023). Mammalian CpG
428 islands, enriched with CpGs, exhibit dynamic methylation states that regulate transcription
429 factor binding and gene expression (Yin et al., 2017; Onuchic et al., 2018). In plants,
430 methylation primarily targets repetitive elements and transposable elements, while
431 invertebrates show reduced methylation, typically restricted to gene bodies with debated
432 functions (Suzuki & Bird, 2008; Law and Jacobsen, 2010; Baduel and Colot, 2021; Cortijo et
433 al., 2014). Some groups, including *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, *C. elegans*, and
434 holometabolous insects like *D. melanogaster*, have lost or greatly reduced DNA methylation
435 (Feng et al., 2010b; Zemach et al., 2010; Provataris et al., 2018). Understanding the different
436 patterns of DNA methylation across species can contribute to our understanding of its
437 different functions and how it contributes to evolutionary processes.

438

439 DNA methylation can not only reveal distinct patterns and functions across taxa but also
440 provide insights into key evolutionary transitions, such as those between Hemimetabolous
441 and Holometabolous insects (Provataris, 2021), vertebrates and invertebrates, and
442 amphibians and reptiles (Klughammer et al., 2023). At finer evolutionary scales, DNA
443 methylation can enhance phylogenetic resolution due to its higher rate of change
444 (epimutations) compared to nucleotide changes, allowing for greater distinction between
445 groups, as has been demonstrated in intra-species comparisons in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and
446 *Zostera marina* (Yao et al., 2023).

447

448 While bisulfite sequencing has led to important discoveries, as demonstrated by many of the
449 empirical studies cited above, long-read sequencing offers even greater resolution for
450 uncovering patterns across taxa and elucidating their relationships (see **Box 1** for discussion
451 in prokaryotes). For example, the issue of SNPs confounding bisulfite sequencing
452 methylation calls – which might lead to erroneous interpretations of patterns and
453 phylogenetic relationships among lineages – is effectively resolved by long-read sequencing.
454 Moreover, the improved resolution of complex regions and ability to phase haplotypes of
455 long-read sequencing has the potential to considerably enhance comparative epigenomic
456 studies in non-model organisms. In this context, pangenome approaches could also hold the
457 key to understanding whether structural genome evolution drives epigenomic diversification
458 among species and during adaptive radiation events.

459

460 Additionally, the ability to detect modifications beyond 5mC might expand our understanding
461 of differential patterns and functions of base modifications among taxa, particularly in groups
462 that lack 5mC. For example, Zhang et al (2023) used Nanopore sequencing to compare
463 6mA patterns among lotus (*Nelumbo nucifera*), *Arabidopsis* and rice. They identified
464 convergent 6mA evolution linked to lineage-specific and duplicate gene divergence,
465 highlighting its role in gene regulatory evolution in plants. Similarly, Lax et al (2024)
466 employed PacBio SMRT sequencing to uncover marked differences in 6mA across fungal

467 phyla, and demonstrated important evolutionary innovations within the Mucorales order.
468 These studies highlight the conserved nature, regulation, and potential evolutionary
469 significance of understudied base modifications such as 6mA.

470
471 A notable opportunity for comparative epigenomics lies in the growing use of long-read
472 sequencing in non-model organisms, often by researchers focused solely on genomic
473 variation. However, these long-read sequencing datasets are often underutilized, with the
474 valuable epigenetic information they contain being overlooked. Beyond shedding light on
475 mutation hotspots, phenotypic variation (e.g., missing heritabilities), and environmental
476 responses (e.g., phenotypic plasticity), this epigenetic data can greatly contribute to
477 comparative epigenomics. If such data is currently being generated in diverse taxa for
478 genomic research, it can be further used to infer patterns and functions of the different DNA
479 methylation modifications across the tree of life, offering insights into evolutionary processes.
480 This presents valuable opportunities for collaboration among research groups from different
481 fields to deepen our understanding of evolution.

482

483 **Challenges when using long-read data**

484

485 Whilst it is clear long-read sequencing is superior to bisulfite sequencing and opens a variety
486 of new research avenues, long-read sequencing still displays some gaps and limitations.

487

488 **Algorithms built on training data:** Currently the “gold standard” base calling algorithms,
489 essential to convert raw sequencing trace files into base calls and modification calls, are
490 primarily built on manufactured data with predetermined modified base quantities. This has
491 led to higher accuracy of CpG DNA methylation calling in species with high genome-wide
492 levels (Kong et al. 2024). Modifications in low quantities can be detected with Nanopore
493 sequencing with considerably less accuracy and a high false positive rate (Kong et al. 2024).
494 This poses a significant risk for the use of long-read data in organisms with known low
495 genome-wide levels of DNA methylation (e.g., insects) and for organisms with unknown
496 levels. CpG DNA methylation detection can also be inaccurate due to diffusion of the signal
497 around the CpG, even in species with high genome-wide levels. However, this is usually
498 accounted for within the algorithms, which can detect and combine the kinetic information
499 from nearby CpGs to increment the confidence of the DNA methylation signal detected
500 (Sigurpalsdottir et al. 2024). However, base calling algorithms are continuing to improve, and
501 it is possible to re-analyze data with newer algorithms to produce more accurate calls. Still,
502 long-term storage of the raw trace files produced from long-read technologies poses a
503 different challenge given their size compared to short-read data.

504

505 **Computational resources and storage:** Compared to short-read sequencing, long-read
506 sequencing produces vast amounts of data requiring extensive storage, high memory, and
507 computational power for processing and analysis (Schmidt & Hilterbrandt, 2017, de Coster et
508 al. 2021). For Nanopore sequencing, even a single sample run on one flow cell can produce
509 over 200 GB of data. Many research institutions have access to high performance computing
510 clusters for analysis, making long-term storage of data the primary issue. Given the
511 movement to open and reproducible science, raw data files must be stored for later use.
512 However, currently only the smaller processed files (post-base calling) are able to be stored

513 in public databases such as the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). At the
514 time of publication, NCBI has confirmed that they do not host these large raw files due to a
515 current lack of demand (Personal Communication, 2024). This means that potentially
516 inaccurate modification calls are the only accessible data for many studies. Whilst it will
517 require an increase in financial investment, it is vital that the raw trace files from these
518 technologies are the primary data that are stored, especially in the era of open data.

519

520 **Financial considerations:** In addition to the cost of raw data storage, long-read sequencing
521 is itself currently more expensive compared to short-read methods, both in terms of
522 sequencing and the necessary infrastructure for analysis. Bisulfite sequencing currently only
523 requires DNA extraction with many sequencing companies providing all additional steps
524 (bisulfite conversion, library preparation etc.) and sequencing for a relatively small cost. This
525 is possible due to the large demand and companies' ability to process samples at scale. As
526 long-read sequencing is currently less common, all components of the process are
527 considerably more expensive. While this is likely the largest hurdle for the adoption of long-
528 read sequencing within the fields of ecology and evolution, as the technology matures, the
529 cost will inevitably decrease.

530

531 **Conclusion**

532

533 Advances in sequencing technologies have consistently broadened the scope of epigenomic
534 research. Long-read sequencing mitigates many limitations of traditional bisulfite
535 sequencing, including its inability to differentiate C/T SNPs from methylation calls, detect
536 specific modifications like 5hmC, or accurately resolve structural variants. By overcoming
537 these challenges, it enables a more nuanced and accurate understanding of DNA
538 methylation and other epigenetic marks. Additionally, as long-read sequencing becomes
539 increasingly common in genomic studies, it offers researchers focused on genomic variation
540 the opportunity to explore epigenetic data, integrating it to gain novel insights into their
541 systems and questions. This integration can enrich genomic studies, revealing overlooked
542 layers of biological complexity.

543

544 The adoption of long-read sequencing in non-model systems will provide novel insights into
545 epigenomic diversity across taxa, the role of structural variation in evolutionary processes,
546 and the mechanisms underpinning phenotypic plasticity and adaptive evolution. Moreover,
547 the ability to phase haplotypes and directly detect a broader array of modifications will
548 enable studies on allele-specific methylation, parent-of-origin effects, and the interplay
549 between genetic and epigenetic variation. While challenges remain—particularly concerning
550 base calling algorithms, raw data storage, and cost—ongoing advancements in algorithms
551 and reductions in sequencing costs promise to make these methods increasingly accessible.
552 The future of epigenomic research is poised to shift dramatically with the broader adoption of
553 long-read sequencing, paving the way for a more integrative understanding of the
554 relationship between epigenetics, the genome, and the environment.

555

556

557

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